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Migrant Workers and Policy Implication within the G20 Framework

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Abstract

This study explores the pivotal role of migrant workers, contributing over 70% to international migrants and projected to generate USD 626 billion in remittances in 2022. Despite their substantial impact, migrant workers face challenges such as modern slavery and discrimination, necessitating urgent international collaboration. Focused on the G20 framework, the research examines how collaborative efforts are vital in addressing issues arising from inadequate worker safeguards in global trade agreements. Amid the COVID-19 pandemic, the G20's recognition of migrant worker concerns becomes a potential catalyst for enhanced international collaboration on social protection, aiming to formulate equitable and sustainable policies. Using a qualitative approach, including case study analysis and G20 document interpretation, this research provides a comprehensive understanding of the complex global issue of migrant worker protection. The concepts of migrant workers and multilateral cooperation are used as the theoretical framework to scrutinise the dynamic of migrant workers in the policy implication within the G20 framework.

Keywords: Migrant Workers, G20, Policy Implication, Multilateral Cooperation

1. Introduction

Migrants, commonly referred to as migrant workers, are individuals who relocate in search of employment opportunities. They typically move from regions with limited job prospects to areas where there is a demand for labour. This migration pattern, noted by geographer E. G. Ravenstein since the 19th century, highlights a trend where people leave their native lands in pursuit of better employment opportunities. Ravenstein's research underscores that the primary motivation for migration is employment, although there are additional factors like family reunification, conflict, and political persecution (Fan, 2020).

As indicated in Fan's (2020) research, migrant workers constitute over 70% of the working-age international migrant population, which includes individuals aged 15 and above. These workers significantly contribute to the economic development of their host countries through their skills, labour, services, and enhanced

competitiveness. Their impact is evident in various aspects, such as remittances, as well as the transfer of skills and knowledge upon their return to their home countries. This contribution is a result of the substantial number of migrant workers who address labour market gaps in destination countries, undertaking roles that may be undesirable or challenging for the local citizens (International Labour Organization, n.d.).

Nations undergoing swift economic expansion and creating more job opportunities often find themselves facing a labour demand that surpasses the available workforce. A case in point is the shortage of labour in agriculture and manufacturing in New Zealand during the 1960s, prompting the influx of low-skilled labour from Tonga and the Cook Islands. Similarly, Mexicans have been migrating north since the 1960s to work in foreign-owned assembly plants near the United States (US) border. Both scenarios share comparable migration patterns, driven by historical connections and geographical proximity (Fan, 2020).

Migrant workers play a significant role in bolstering a country's economy, particularly as they predominantly hail from low and middle-income nations. The funds sent back by these migrant workers, known as remittances, serve as a crucial financial support system for the economies of their countries of origin. According to World Economic Forum data, global remittances are projected to reach USD 626 billion in 2022, reflecting a 5% increase from the previous year (Broom, 2023).

India, as the leading source of migrant workers, stands out for generating the highest global remittances. World Bank data for 2021 reveals that remittances from Indian migrant workers amounted to USD 100 billion, reflecting a 7.5% increase from the previous year and contributing 3% to India's Gross Domestic Product (GDP). This figure surpasses the remittances from other major countries with high numbers of migrant workers, including Mexico (USD 60 billion), China (USD 51 billion), the Philippines (USD 38 billion), Egypt (USD 32 billion), and Pakistan (USD 29 billion) (Ani, 2022).

In Indonesia, migrant workers also make a substantial contribution to the country's income. In 2018, Indonesian migrant workers contributed a record-high amount of USD 11.2 billion to state income through remittances (International Organization for Migration Indonesia, n.d.). The primary source of remittance for Indonesian migrant workers was Saudi Arabia, accounting for USD 2.8 billion, with approximately 837,000 PMI working there. Besides Saudi Arabia, significant remittances also originated from Malaysia, Taiwan, and Hong Kong, amounting to USD 2.5 billion, USD 1.47 billion, and USD 1.37 billion, respectively (Gianie, 2023).

While migrant workers contribute significantly to income generation, they also grapple with a range of challenges, including modern slavery, discrimination, breaches of employment contracts, torture, violence, and hazardous working conditions characterized by filth and danger. These difficulties are more prevalent among migrant workers with lower skill levels. Additionally, migrant workers often confront issues related to their legal status. In certain countries, obtaining legal recognition as a migrant worker can be arduous, leading some to work illegally. Illegal status poses obstacles for migrant workers in accessing healthcare services, and they may not receive health or employment insurance from their employers due to the uncertainty of their status. This situation has direct implications for the occupational health and safety risks faced by migrant workers, especially those who lack awareness of the laws governing their status and the rights they should be entitled to (Norredam & Agyemang, 2019).

A study conducted by Kalayaan, a Non-Governmental Organization (NGO) focusing on human rights issues, particularly those concerning domestic migrant workers in the United Kingdom (UK), revealed that among 1,000 migrant workers surveyed, a significant number faced various forms of abuse. Specifically, 84% experienced psychological violence, 54% were subjected to confinement abroad, 38% endured physical torture, and 10% encountered sexual harassment. Kalayaan's findings also highlighted that 49% of migrant workers had their passports confiscated by their employers, limiting their ability to travel (Sengupta, 2007).

Similar challenges are observed in Indonesia, where a report from the Indonesian Migrant Worker Protection Agency indicates that from 2000 to 2023, they facilitated the repatriation of 1,937 deceased Indonesian Migrant Workers and 3,377 ailing Indonesian migrant workers. This suggests that, on average, two deceased Indonesian

migrant workers and four Indonesian migrant workers facing health issues, memory loss, depression, and even disabilities are repatriated to Indonesia daily (Gianie, 2023).

Hence, it can be asserted that the matter of migrant workers is a pressing concern demanding prompt and precise resolution, given their substantial representation in the workforce across numerous nations. While migrant workers play a pivotal role in the global economy, they frequently confront significant challenges related to labour rights and living conditions. Addressing this issue requires collaborative efforts between countries. The G20 framework emerges as a strategic platform for addressing various facets of migrant worker concerns, given that the majority of G20 member countries serve as both sources and destinations for migrant workers. There is an immediate need to formulate shared policies, exchange information, and implement concrete measures that G20 nations can undertake to enhance the protection and well-being of migrant workers, establishing a more equitable and sustainable foundation for cross-border labour mobility. Therefore, this article aims to spotlight the migrant worker issue and explore the repercussions of policies implemented within the G20 framework.

2. Method

This qualitative research focuses on a comprehensive analysis of a single case study concerning migrant workers' issues within the G20 framework and the implementation of policies. The methodology involves gathering outcomes or hypotheses derived from prior research, followed by the interpretation of these results. Our analysis of the G20 framework's approach to addressing migrant worker issues relies on the examination of documents issued by the G20, serving as the basis for evaluating its policy recommendations. In addition to official G20 documents, our references include journal articles and online sources to provide a thorough analysis of this topic. The process of data analysis is conducted concurrently with the collection of data from various documents.

3. Theoretical Framework

3.1. Migrant Workers

Migration is an activity of a person or group that moves from its place of origin to the place where money becomes its destination. If the activity has crossed the international border, it is commonly called international migration. People who move to their destination are generally known as migrants. However, not everyone who moves is called a migrant. Those people could be stated as migrants if they have lived in their destination for more than a year (Kompasiana, 2023).

Based on the "Glossary on Migration" by the International Organization of Migration (IOM), according to the United Nations Conventions on The Law of Human Rights of Migrant Workers and Their Family Members, migrant workers settle called a person who works or dedicate themselves to work where they do not become the citizen. Migrant workers or labour migrants are also referred to as a person who move (migration) from one to another place to get a certain thing (IOM UN Migration, 2019). In this certain condition, the definition of migrant workers expands for someone who has migrated internationally and has definitively become more inclusive. By the expanding of meaning, migrant workers have stated as a person, either who has not worked or who will look for a job and a person who has worked regardless of the original purpose or the main purpose of that person is to migrate. However, migrant workers do not include border workers, members of liberal professions and/or artists, sailors and specific persons who come to get an education or training (International Labour Organization, 2021).

IOM has categorised migrant workers as economic migrants. This classification encompasses various groups such as entrepreneurs, contractual migrant workers, settled migrant workers, highly skilled migrant workers, immigrant investors, project-specific workers, seasonal migrant workers, and temporary migrant workers. A migrant worker is defined as an individual who moves from a certain place to get a job, whereas the term 'economic migrants' refers to the larger category, including a personal activity entrance to a certain country for

doing an economic activity such as investors or businessmen. Nevertheless, the term 'economic migrants' be able to be conceived tighter as a part of the 'economic migrants' category (Fauzan, 2020).

3.2. Multilateral Cooperations

Multilateral cooperation has collaboration involvement with all the member countries. This collaboration consists of several developed countries and developing countries. During the development of multilateral cooperation, there is a new dynamic emerged that exists in informal groups within international politics area. The emergence of informal cooperation groups will emphasize the collaboration of member countries in addressing global issues. Therefore, it could be stated as a form of collective management responding to global issues (Cooper & Momani, 2014). The policy coordination at the multilateral level also becomes a characteristic of multilateral cooperation.

One of the main features of multilateral cooperation is policy coordination at the multilateral level. This coordination is key in maintaining the continuity and effectiveness of cooperation between one and other countries. Facing complicated global issues, multilateral cooperation offers a platform where the countries able to work together attain mutual benefit solutions.

The emergence of multipolarity is the result of a decrease in the concentration of economic activity within the international system and an increase in concentration beyond the previous core. Compared to unipolar systems, multipolar systems generate a bigger value of cooperation. However, the cooperation system becomes more difficult as more countries have different preferences, interests, and beliefs. The G20 is a form of cooperation that is reflected in multilateralism. The G20 was established to encourage cooperation between one and other countries and is held informally with changes of leadership arrangement that always change every year and the secretariat provided by the leader (Wade, 2011). Through the G20, the countries are provided meetings and gatherings, doing a dialogue, and working together in formulating a global policy that eclipsed bigger challenges in the world.

The G20 is not only a place where the developed and developing countries interact with one another, but this is also a reflection of the spirit of multilateralism that is necessary to carry out global issues. In this context, this is important to recognize that multilateral cooperation is not an easy process. The challenges and complexities require a strong commitment, precise a diplomacy strategy, and the ability to figure out a solution among diverse interests.

In the presence of multilateral collaboration, all countries have an opportunity to handle the differences and build mutual agreements. Multilateral cooperation is not only about solving a problem but also about building the foundations for long-term global stability. By constantly developing and strengthening the multilateral instruments of cooperation, the world effectively responds the issues involving all humanity. Facing global challenges such as climate change, economic inequality, and humanitarian crises, multilateral cooperation will essentially create a more just world, sustainable, and safe for all.

4. Results and Discussions

4.1. Globalisation and Migration: A Recent Trend

Globalisation involves the integration of countries, including economic integration, the transfer of policies across national borders, the exchange of knowledge and culture, and the dissemination of power. The concept of globalisation has evolved with diverse definitions over the years, some associating it with progress, development, stability, integration, and cooperation, while others link it to decline, colonisation, and destabilisation. Moreover, globalisation is a dynamic phenomenon, signifying a continuous process that evolves alongside the development of human society (Al-Rodhan & Stoudmann, 2006). Thus, globalisation can be characterised as the broadening, deepening, and acceleration of worldwide connectivity in all aspects of contemporary social life (Czaika & de Haas, 2014).

Globalisation refers to the establishment of strong economic, informational, political, cultural, and other interdependent connections between countries, which play a crucial role in shaping future development. Among the significant manifestations of these connections are migration flows, denoting the movement of people between countries resulting from the disparate development of the world economy, disparities in economic conditions and opportunities across nations, varying degrees of engagement in the processes of modernisation and globalisation, and the requirements of the global labour market (Zubiashvili, 2017).

Czaika and de Haas (2014) view globalisation as both a technological and political phenomenon. Technology plays a role in diminishing the costs associated with air transportation and communication, facilitating easier movement of people between different locations. This trend is reminiscent of the 1960s when the advancement of revolutionary transportation systems and communication technology acted as prerequisites for a 'migration explosion'. The surge in migration is also fuelled by the escalating demand for foreign workers in specific regions worldwide, as exemplified by the post-war history of Europe, intricately linked to the emergence of large-scale migration flows directed towards Western European countries from various global regions (Zubiashvili, 2017). Furthermore, the reduction of restrictions on international trade through free trade agreements has fostered greater global interconnectedness, affording people increased freedom to migrate and access information technology (Čiarnienė & Kumpikaitė-Valiūnienė, 2008).

Moreover, this process facilitates migrants in reinforcing established connections and transferring funds to and from the destination country. The rise in literacy and educational levels aligns with technological advancements that facilitate access to global information through television, mobile phones, and internet networks, thereby simplifying the migration process (Czaika & de Haas, 2014). Consequently, in the current phase of global development, there exists a close interrelation between the flow of goods and capital and human migration movements. Thus, globalisation and migration sometimes exhibit distinct geographical directions, complement each other, and serve as both conditions and consequences of one another (Zubiashvili, 2017).

Regarding migrant workers, globalisation presents an opportunity for individuals to pursue a better quality of life in foreign countries, particularly when the ease of movement is facilitated by various modes of transportation and heightened global demand for labour. Migrant workers typically engage in informal sector employment, often under a permanent or contractual work arrangement. It is not uncommon for these workers to lack adequate welfare provisions, as they may not receive benefits such as health insurance, severance pay, or pensions. This leaves migrant workers in a precarious position, especially when confronted with uncertain circumstances such as job termination, illness, or workplace accidents, and when encountering challenges in securing employment in the destination country (Misra, 2007).

In 2005, the termination of the multifibre arrangement under the regulations of the World Trade Organization (WTO) had a profound impact on global trade agreements. Unfortunately, this led to the displacement of many female contract workers in countries like Bangladesh, Indonesia, and Swaziland, particularly in the textile and garment industry. Due to the lack of adequate severance pay, unemployment insurance, and job prospects, many young female workers became vulnerable to exploitation by labour recruiters. These recruiters sought to capitalise on the challenging circumstances faced by these workers by offering overseas employment opportunities that they might otherwise reject due to a lack of viable alternatives.

Global trade agreements, often deficient in adequate labour standards and protections, frequently lead to the exploitation of migrant workers. An illustrative example is the US African Growth and Opportunity Act (AGOA), which prompted heightened investment in Africa, resulting in the growth of textile and garment factories within Export Processing Zones (EPZ) in nations like Uganda. To occupy low-wage positions in these factories, agents from Uganda and Kenya enlist young female workers from Kenya. Upon reaching Uganda, as documented by Kenyan labour unions, numerous women encountered exploitation and were subjected to trafficking for forced labour and other exploitative activities, including sexual practices. Referred to as 'AGOA Girls,' certain female workers find themselves in precarious circumstances in Uganda, given their migrant status and the lack of labour law protection in the country (Misra, 2007).

Currently, data from the International Labour Organization (ILO) in 2021 indicates an upward trajectory in the trend of migrant workers. In 2019, the tally of migrant workers stood at 169 million individuals, compared to 150 million in 2013. This figure is anticipated to continue its ascent. Approximately 58.5% of migrant workers are male, with the remaining 41.5% being female. The lower representation of female migrant workers highlights the challenges they confront, including gender discrimination and the domestic responsibilities of being a wife, necessitating a balance between work and family commitments. Additionally, migrant workers continue to be largely comprised of adults, constituting approximately 86%, while teenagers and the elderly make up only around 10% and 3.5%, respectively (International Labour Organization, 2021). Considering the insights into migrant workers and the available data, it becomes evident that globalisation serves as an avenue for migrants to secure improved employment opportunities. However, these migrant workers are not exempt from challenges, including exploitation, discrimination, and insufficient health and employment insurance. Teeple (2000) suggests that globalization, also interpreted as a 'triumph of capitalism,' acts as the impetus behind the expansion of the global labour market and the ensuing competition in wages. This competition, in turn, leads to migrant workers obtaining minimal welfare benefits.

4.2. Dynamic Issues of Migrant Workers in G20

The migrant workers are the most attention topic that is discussed continuously in G20. This topic is based on the dynamics of development global issue level that impacted on migration flows. The large influx of refugees brings significant problems in many sectors, especially in the economic sectors. Hence, a comprehensive coordination approach for major countries to solve these problems is needed by considering their long-term impacts (G20 2015, 2015b). Many ways in engagement groups of G20 2015 have agreed that there must be cooperation between the members and admit the right of refugees to work, provide skills development and cooperate with various international institutions through job opening programs for the refugees (G20 2015, 2015a). If it is done, the existence of these immigrants will have a positive impact on economic growth, especially in filling the demand for domestic labour. Therefore, we can see that G20 emphasises the importance of cooperation. It is not only increasing the capacity of skills for refugees but also cooperation in providing employment.

Furthermore, in G20 2015 in China, it was restated in the communique that migration worker is the answer to the opportunities and challenges regarding the creation of labour markets, reducing inequalities and encouraging inclusive labour to force this migration could be managed properly (G20 2016, 2016). To create these growth and development efforts, need anticipatory actions regarding changing skills of working requirements, supporting entrepreneurship, encouraging decent and safe work, and strengthening social protection systems. The G20 members must promote the internship quality programs in terms of increasing the quality and quantity.

The G20 2017 Summit was held in Germany while a G20 Africa partnership program was launched. This partnership is the result of aspirations from African countries where migration activities occur in their territories due to high economic inequality and poverty (G20 2017, 2017b). In this partnership, the G20 seeks to drive economic growth through inclusive and sustainable development, increasing the value of investment and education assistance to improve people's skills. In addition to the agenda of the "G20 Labour and Employment Ministers Meeting 2017" has declared a fair and integrated policy regarding the labour market for migrants and refugees. Regarding the practice, they hope that it becomes a guideline for G20 countries as the implementation could be adjusted again to the national conditions and policies of each country. The policy particularly discusses the provision of access to the employment market, the development of workers' capabilities, the promotion of decent work and letters of economic and community acceptance (G20 2017, 2017a).

Meanwhile, in the next round of the G20 in 2018 held in Argentina, less agreement was created about migration issues. The G20 Leaders declaration is concerned about the express occurrence of massive migration flows which also had an impact on many aspects, one of them being about economic aspect. The country's leaders emphasised the need for joint action to solve the problem and swiftly respond to the needs of immigrants. Although each country's economy is stable and experiencing growth, in reality, the labour market still faces a challenge. One of these challenges is the significant migration program. This matter needed to create a

framework and innovative policy. The detailing issue will be considered in the next round of the G20 (G20 2018, 2018).

The attention to migrant workers issues in the G20 was continuously discussed in the Labour Minister's Meeting in 2019. According to the declaration at the ministerial level, the G20 is concerned about migrant's average work in the informal sector. In addition, the G20 Osaka Leaders' Declaration emphasized that the large number of refugees impacts global matters, humanitarian, political, social, and economic sectors. The G20 has emphasised that cooperation is crucial to address the root causes of displacement. and fill humanitarian needs. This issue's emphasis on increasing migrants and the impact on several sectors are sustainable issues that have been discussed at the G20 (G20 2019, 2019).

The G20 meeting in 2020 became the most important meeting response to the COVID-19 pandemic. In 2020, the G20 attention to the migrant workers are vulnerable workers affected by COVID-19. The cooperation to mitigate the impact of the pandemic is an important step that was decided in the G20 Declaration in 2020. Furthermore, in line with the previous meeting, this G20 meeting has agreed to help solve the problem of the rising of migrants (G20 2020, 2020). The results of the G20 meeting in 2020 were a foundation for the 2021 meeting which was still marked by several impacts due to the pandemic.

Meeting in 2021, the G20 pay attention to the improved flexible, crisis-responsive and adequate social protection systems that are accessible to everyone during the COVID-19 pandemic. Special emphasis is placed on temporary or part-time workers, informal workers, self-employed, migrants, and low-income workers. One of the solutions sought in dealing with the impact of the pandemic is to encourage decent work for migrant workers. The policies taken here include expanding the social security rights for migrant workers. In the G20 leadership declaration, it was explained that the global economy is facing new challenges related to migration as a result of the pandemic. The measurement supports the inclusion of migrants, including migrant workers. For example, the G20 recognizes how important it is to prevent migrant smuggling and irregular migration flows as part of a comprehensive approach to safe, orderly, and orderly migration flows (G20 2021, 2021).

Furthermore, in 2022 the G20 observed that digital technology and automation have changed the world of work. Existing disparities in many countries and conditions for migrant workers have been exacerbated by the COVID-19 pandemic. It is significant to prevent the negative impact of current trends on the labour market. The G20 leaders agreed to support the full inclusion of migrant workers at the Bali Summit 2020 (G20 2022, 2022). This shows that the challenges of the job market are not only the impact of COVID-19, but also the improvement of digital technology provides its challenges for increasing human resource capacity in the job market.

The delineation above shows that the attention to the issue of migrant workers is motivated by several developments in international dynamics along with the increasing flow of migrants. In addition, the presence of the COVID-19 pandemic has presented some challenges for the job market which of course not only provide challenges for economic performance, but also the job market. The vulnerable position of migrant workers is a challenge for the G20 to strengthen cooperation between countries in dealing with this issue. The inclusion of the migrant workers' agenda declaration provides the number of policy implications that must be taken by G20 countries in dealing with the current issue of migrant workers.

The migrant workers' issue will not only explain employment matters, such as the labour market and raising the capacity of the workers but also the related issue tied to social protection. G20 member countries are not only responsible for the world economy but also play an important role in policy responses to migration challenges and opportunities impacting migrants, their countries of origin, their transit countries, and the global economy. Concerning the migration flows in G20 countries, here is a diagram illustrating migration flows to some G20 countries in 2010-2020:

Figure 1: The migration flow to several countries of G20 in 2015-2020 (in thousand)

Source: (OECD/ILO/IOM/UNHCR, 2021), managed by authors

The diagram above shows that from 2015-2020 there is a trend in different levels of migration flows among G20 member countries. There was a decrease in migration flows from 2019 to 2020. The US was the top destination country, with over 1 million migrant visits in 2020. In addition, Germany ranked second with nearly 1 million migrants, most of whom were temporary and came from other EU member states. With nearly about 800,000 migrant workers in Saudi Arabia in 2020, the country ranked third (OECD/ILO/IOM/UNHCR, 2021).

Most labour immigration policies across the world select immigrants based on their professional profile. Jobs are classified into categories that require either low-skilled or high-skilled workers, depending on the level of formal education, training, and work experience required to perform a particular job. The immigration systems in high-income countries generally favour workers who aspire to work in higher-skilled or higher-paying jobs and impose restrictions on those who wish to work in lower-skilled jobs. The immigration system is not straightforward and should be constantly adapted to meet the rapidly changing external environment. The government needs to consider not only the role of migrant workers but also other possible solutions to labour demand in important sectors. This includes whether demand for local workers can be met by raising wages, improving working conditions, or using labour-saving technology (Fernández-Reino et al., 2020).

Migration dynamics tend to provide a wide array of economic benefits, although the negative impacts are limited. However, the overall impact of immigration on domestic employment and wages remains limited. On the other hand, because many immigrants tend to be of productive working age, immigration increases the number of working-age residents in the total population. In addition, developed countries that are popular destinations have selective immigration policies. This approach is attributed to the demand for increased education of immigrants to find the criteria for employability in destination countries, especially developed countries. Therefore, it is important to improve the quality of skills of migrant workers. Immigration can make an essential contribution to labour force growth, but governments must be able to balance labour needs with the skills of immigrants. In this regard, more must be done to use migrants' skills better and adapt labour mobility management systems to employers' needs. (Kadkoy & Sak, 2019).

Those delineation shows the variation of workers' positions also the scope of employment needs to be given more attention for every country. In this method, access to the proper work becomes attention in facing the issue of migrant workers. The sufficient skill that is suitable for the job offering in the destination country becomes an important thing. Access to the proper work is an issue that is a concern in the meeting of G20. Seeing this

condition, G20 as a multilateral forum gives a chance for every country member to transparently communicate with each other regarding migrant worker matters. The mapping of skill issues of migrant workers that are faced by the country of G20 in the destination country or the country of origin of the migrant is important. As the forum is the place for meeting and gathering from developed countries, the G20 can give hope to the consolidation and collaboration to solve the problem related to the migrant workers' skills.

Regarding raising the quality of migrant workers, the other important thing related to the policy of migrant workers is social protection. This important issue is significant as remembering of COVID-19 pandemic gives a severe blow to every country addressing the problem of migrant workers during the pandemic. Several countries have expanded social security measures to protect vulnerable groups such as migrant workers and refugees during the COVID-19 pandemic. For instance, the Republic of Korea has expanded benefits for migrant workers who need to be quarantined, while Saudi Arabia offers free COVID-19 testing and treatment for migrant workers in abnormal conditions. France and Spain have extended migrant workers' residence permits for three months in 2020 to ensure that they have access to healthcare services. Portugal provides certain rights and support, such as health services, social support, employment, and housing to non-national workers, including asylum seekers whose applications are still being processed. Brazil offers an emergency monthly basic income for three months, which includes migrant workers who have not regularized their status. (OECD/ILO/IOM/UNHCR, 2021).

The relationship between migration status and working status between the worker and employer are the important factors that influence working access towards social protections. Many programs are in line with the migrant workers that are tied to the permit to live of migrant workers with their employer. The migrant farmworkers in Canada who obtain a health ID under their Seasonal Agricultural Worker Program (SAWP) are entitled to direct access to most provincial public health insurance systems. Temporary migrant workers often find it difficult to access public health services, immunisation programs, or vaccinations. Despite their right to essential services, they face significant challenges, such as the fear of losing their current or future rights. To address this issue, migrant-sending countries usually try to reach bilateral social security agreements with migrant-receiving countries. Canada has signed 57 social security agreements, 53 of which are still in effect (Hennebry, 2014).

Besides creating an agreement of social warranty bilaterally, there is also another effort to protect the migrant workers. In the past several years one of the most significant expansions and prominent that have been done to several countries is taking an action to give a social warranty to those who work overseas by strengthening their steps to the large support. Full action will be done in this institutional and operational framework (International Organization for Migration, 2017).

Social protection for migrant workers become an important aspect during the COVID-19 pandemic and after the pandemic. The vulnerable position of migrant workers requires concrete steps from every country to take a stand in providing social protection. From the picture above, cooperation between countries can be an alternative to creating a good social protection mechanism for migrant workers. As a multilateral cooperation forum, the G20 is a forum for member countries to further strengthen cooperation between member countries in terms of creating effective social protection mechanisms for migrant workers. This is not a simple matter, because the cooperation is carried out context of social protection which needs to look at the condition of social protection at the domestic level of each member country. Hence, in this case, cooperation which is a collective effort is also accompanied by policy efforts at the domestic level of member countries.

5. Conclusion

Migrant workers play a crucial role in the global economy, contributing over 70% to international migrants within the working-age group, with anticipated remittances reaching USD 626 billion in 2022. Despite the significant impact of migrant workers, they face challenges related to modern slavery, discrimination, and precarious working conditions. Lower-skilled workers encounter additional obstacles, often resorting to illegal employment due to legal status issues. Addressing these challenges necessitates prompt and accurate action, emphasising international collaboration.

International migration, an integral aspect of globalisation, involves individuals seeking livelihoods outside their native countries, particularly as economic migrant workers. Collaborative efforts at a global level, especially within the G20 framework, are deemed crucial for addressing global concerns related to safeguarding migrant workers. Challenges such as exploitation, discrimination, and job insecurity arise from the absence of adequate worker safeguards in international trade agreements.

The G20, recognising the significance of migrant worker issues, has focused on comprehensive coordination in meetings. The impact of the COVID-19 pandemic further underscores the vulnerability of migrant workers, with efforts in subsequent G20 meetings emphasising adaptable social protection systems and improved working conditions. Acknowledging the influence of digital technology on migrant workers in 2022, the G20 advocates for their complete integration.

Migration data from 2015 to 2020 indicates fluctuations in levels among G20 nations, with a marked decline in 2020. Developed countries generally have more receptive labour immigration policies for high-skilled workers. While immigration has a limited impact on domestic employment and wages, it contributes significantly to labour force growth.

Addressing the challenges faced by migrant workers requires enhancing their skills and aligning immigration policies with workforce needs. The primary focus should be on social protection, especially considering the repercussions of the COVID-19 pandemic. The G20 is viewed as a potential platform for reinforcing international collaboration on social protection for migrant workers, playing a significant role in responding to migration challenges and opportunities. Sustained cooperation among G20 nations is crucial for formulating equitable and sustainable policies to enhance the protection and welfare of migrant workers.

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